

Mitigating Moral Distress for Resuscitation Team Healthcare Providers

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Background

- ❖ Moral distress is described as an uneasy feeling that comes from providing care that goes against an individual's moral code.
- ❖ It is a phenomenon that can contribute to health care provider burnout.
- ❖ Healthcare providers who respond to cardiac arrest events often experience the highest form of moral distress.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this project was to implement post resuscitation debriefing processes to mitigate moral distress among resuscitation team health care providers (RTHPs) in a 504-bed non-profit, suburban, acute care hospital.

Methods

A retrospective study design was used for this quality improvement project. RTHPs were surveyed about a post resuscitation debriefing process which included:

- ❖ A 20-minute education on moral distress
- ❖ An introduction to the 4 A's to Rise Above Moral Distress debriefing process
- ❖ A Moment of Silence (The Pause) held after unsuccessful resuscitations to honor the life of the patient and the work of the team.

Demographic data and perspectives on the effectiveness of the three interventions were analyzed.

Framework

Results

- ❖ 39/99 RTHP survey responses, 28 complete surveys were analyzed. Attrition rate: 61%
- ❖ RTHP survey respondents: RNs: 71.4%, RTs: 17.8%, Chaplains 10.7%
- ❖ Unsuccessful resuscitations = 8, Moments of silence performed = 6, Rate of utilization: 75%
- ❖ Resuscitation attendees = 48, 4 A's self debriefing process use = 38, Rate of utilization: 86%

Perspective on Moral Distress Education & Moment of Silence

- Q1 The moral distress education helped you to understand what moral distress is.
- Q2 How useful was the education in assisting you to feel more comfortable in talking about moral distress with RTHPs?
- Q3 The moment of silence allowed you to personally acknowledge the life of the patient.
- Q4 The moment of silence allowed you to personally acknowledge the work of the team.

Resuscitation Team: Cardiac Arrest Event & Moment of Silence

Innovations

Project application unexpected outcome:

- ❖ The Moment of silence was implemented by the health care team for patients who survived the initial resuscitation but did not survive to discharge. The patients passed after being made Do Not Resuscitate by family. In many instances the family were present for the Moment of Silence.
- ❖ The rate of utilization was 15/18 = 83%

Recommendations

- ❖ Implement moral distress education and moment of silence to nursing units experiencing difficult end of life care situations – modified to care needs.
- ❖ Create policy/protocol to ensure consistency of education and use of interventions.
- ❖ Recommend pre- and post- moral distress assessment to track effectiveness of interventions.

Conclusions

- ❖ Experiences of moral distress can be mitigated with interventions that foster team building, peer support, and debriefing. Inclusion of all health care members promotes trusting supportive care environments.
- ❖ Dissemination of results provided at staff meetings to RTHPs and administration.